

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF THE AGRO-INDUSTRY NETWORK BASED ON THE INTRODUCTION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article studies the theoretical foundations of the introduction of digital technologies in the development of the agro-industrial sector in our country. The existing problems of clustering entities operating in the agro-industrial sector are extensively analyzed using the SWOT analysis method, and scientific and practical proposals and recommendations are developed.

Key words: agro-industry, digital transformation, digital technology, SWOT analysis, potential, information system.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada mamlakatimiz agrosanoat majmuasini rivojlantirishga raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etishning nazariy asoslari ko'rib chiqilgan. SWOT tahlil usulidan foydalangan holda agrosanoat majmuasi subyektlarini klasterlashning mavjud muammolari atroficha tahlil etilib, ilmiy-amaliy taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: agrosanoat kompleksi, raqamli transformatsiya, raqamli texnologiyalar, SWOT tahlil, salohiyat, axborot tizimi.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются теоретические основы внедрения цифровых технологий в развитие агропромышленного комплекса нашей страны. С использованием метода SWOT-анализа подробно анализируются существующие проблемы кластеризации субъектов агропромышленного комплекса, разрабатываются научно-практические предложения и рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: агропромышленный комплекс, цифровая трансформация, цифровые технологии, SWOT-анализ, потенциал, информационная система.

INTRODUCTION

Developed countries have passed the land-saving stage of the problem system in the production of agricultural products and have entered the next stages of development. One of the main criteria for their suitability for this status is the value of the digital evolution index. According to its specific characteristics, the digital evolution index is divided into 4 groups. Group 1 is called the leaders, and the characteristics of the group indicate a high level of digital development and rapid growth. This group includes Singapore, Great Britain, New Zealand, Estonia, Hong Kong, Japan and Israel. Group 2 is called "slow growth", and is characterized by a characteristically long period of dynamic growth, but currently the pace of development has slowed down. It is expected that they will lag behind the leaders in digitalization due to the lack of dynamic innovation. This group also includes South Korea, Australia, as well as Western European and Scandinavian countries. The overall level of digitalization is lower than the first two groups, but at the same time it is characterized by stable digital development dynamics. Group 3 of the index includes China, Kenya, Russia, India, Malaysia, the Philippines, Indonesia, Brazil, Colombia, Chile, Mexico. The current situation in these countries may attract investors and even allow them to join the group of leaders. The last group, group 4 is called "problematic", and the nature of the group is characterized by slow growth and a low level of development, mainly due to numerous obstacles associated with internal factors. This group of countries includes South Africa, Peru, Egypt, Greece, and Pakistan [1].

Relying on foreign experience in assessing modern production parameters is one of the main sources. When it comes to the application of digital technologies in the economic sectors of developed countries, its efficiency indicators in various sectors of the economy can be taken as information. Because digital technologies serve the complex development of all sectors of the economy and determine the overall state of development. In this sense, when linking the level of economic growth with digital technologies, in the research work of many leading scientific research centers and research institutes of the world, a certain sector of the economy is not limited to the analysis of results related to this sector only [2].

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Theoretical and practical issues of effective use of land and other production resources in agriculture are based on several sectoral knowledge. In this regard, an approach from an agrarian point of view alone does not offer any solutions. According to the research scientist Max Weber [3], who conducted scientific research in the agricultural sector, in the future it will not be possible to achieve results only by improving the quality of land resources and increasing the efficiency of labor resources, but only by using intellectual technologies to increase production volumes. Dutch researcher Jaap Jan Schröder emphasizes the increasing role of the chemical industry in agricultural production. Researcher Dunstan Gabriel Msuya, in his scientific research on the Canadian agricultural system, states that the creation of varieties resistant to the environmental environment and the development of genetic engineering will become one of the main factors determining the development of agriculture. Russian economist Yugai A.M. emphasizes in his research that repeated crops and crop rotation in the Russian Federation have a significant impact on production volumes. Also, scientists of our country have considered the issues of land use efficiency across regions [4], the use of econometric modeling in assessing the value of land resources.

The concept of digital transformation is seen as one of the main processes not only in agriculture or land use issues, but also in ensuring general socio-economic development. In our country, complex measures are being taken to actively develop the digital economy, widely introduce modern information and communication technologies in all sectors and areas, primarily in public administration, education, healthcare and agriculture.

Digital transformation is being implemented on a global scale, both in the economy and at the level of individual sectors. Because international corporations are introducing new technologies and their business models, digital transformation, in order to maintain their leading position in their fields by creating insurmountable technological barriers to their competitors.

In the conditions of the digital economy, a new approach to economy in agriculture, linking production costs with product quality and production efficiency is required. And this can be achieved largely by applying new forms and methods of econometric and statistical accounting, new methodologies of digital technology.

The use of digital technologies in agricultural production and management, the creation of material and technical support at the required level, their arming with modern digital technology, and the deepening of economic reforms in the agricultural sector are of great importance, further increasing the sense of ownership of land and property, and the development of mechanisms for organizing and optimally regulating production based on entrepreneurship, business, new ownership and the digital economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research utilizes comparative and statistical methods, as well as system analysis and synthesis methods. The information base for the study is derived from official statistical data and foreign sources.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

“Digital Uzbekistan 2030” strategy aims to form a modern, complex digital system based on the requirements that must be met, taking into account the current global development mechanisms. What could be the minimum level of development for the agricultural production process if the measures listed in the priority areas of digital infrastructure development are implemented? The minimum level can be understood as the general, that is, public use of the created opportunities. In this regard, it is necessary to pay attention to the following aspect, namely the presence of a platform for receiving and exchanging sectoral information. This naturally strengthens the advertising market in this area, leads to qualitative and quantitative improvements due to the accumulation and exchange of experience, increased competition, the use of open data on the current and future state of certain factors affecting product production, and contributes to the formation and expansion of the knowledge base.

The introduction of modern information and communication technologies to increase land use efficiency in agriculture, reduce the cost of products and increase export potential remains one of the priority areas directly related to the development of agricultural production. It is proven that digitalization gives a 2 percent higher efficiency than the use of new management methods, and in both cases the implementation of one or another factor is effective. The greatest effect in this process is their joint application, which provides the producer with 26 percent economic growth. In our country, special attention is paid to the productive use of land in the production of agricultural products. According to the technical and economic stages of agricultural development, the problems of saving labor and land are not the most prominent, but rather, it can be observed that more attention is paid to other factors of the effective use of existing land resources. For example, the intensive production process. A number of foreign scientists have emphasized the effectiveness of organizing

the intensive production process using digital technologies. Thus, a solution can be found by implementing the “Smart” agriculture project.

An example of “smart” agricultural technologies is the IoT system. That is, IoT (Internet of Things) is a system for automating management processes and exchanging large amounts of information using various “smart devices”. The areas of application of this technology in agriculture include farming, farms, greenhouses, resource management, storage of agricultural products, transport management, and others. To assess the minimum efficiency of measures taken to develop digital technologies in the real sector of the economy in the production process of agricultural products, we will pay attention to the following.

We divide the production process into two, primary and secondary production. One of the important aspects of digital transformation is not only ensuring the efficiency of raw material production and its export, but also supporting the production of secondary products. For example, with the introduction of digital technologies, the volume of agricultural production has increased, labor productivity has been achieved. There is also a second side to this, namely, the issue of targeted allocation of freed labor resources arises. In other economic sectors of the region, the demand for these labor resources is not sufficient. In this case, it is natural that the effectiveness of modern technologies used will be only one-sided. Thus, the production of secondary products and their export is considered the simplest solution and the intended goal is achieved.

As part of the measures taken to create a favorable environment for the national market of digital technologies and develop promising „digital“ startups, it is necessary to develop local technological and software digital tools used in the production of agricultural products, taking into account local capabilities, geographical, ecological, geological, biological characteristics of the region. The minimum stage of this requires determining the optimal solution for sufficiently mastering the use of modern technological and software digital tools used in the agricultural sector by foreign developed countries.

Our government pays special attention to the effective use of resources through the introduction of digital technologies in agriculture. In particular, it is planned to increase the number of automated devices in reservoirs, regional and inter-district irrigation systems, district irrigation systems from 269 to 400 units over the next two years. It is planned to increase the share of satellite navigation technologies in the management of agricultural machinery from 10% to 50% in 2021-2022.

The main implementation mechanism for measures to expand digital infrastructure in the agro-industrial sector is the organization of a system of connection to high-speed information transmission and reception networks, fiber-optic and wireless communication.

In the conditions of the new Uzbekistan, the agricultural service system will be closely interconnected with such very important sectors as irrigation, land reclamation, and breeding. After all, it is impossible to imagine Uzbek agriculture without the high level of development of these sectors. In particular, a SWOT analysis of the development of agro-industrial sectors is presented (table 1).

Table 1. SWOT analysis of the development of the agro-industry network.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none">the implementation of special agricultural reforms and the creation of legal foundations for the development of agriculture;the adoption of a separate Law „On Agriculture“ for the development of agriculture;the formation of land and property owners on the basis of the law;the introduction of agriculture into the form of entrepreneurship and the satisfaction of the interests of the people, the main link of society;the full formation of skills in working with land among peasants and farmers;rapid adaptation as a small-scale commodity producer, not prone to bankruptcy;the focus of its activities on generating income.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">the lack of improvement of the necessary economic mechanisms for the development of agricultural holdings;the lack of a clearly regulated, convenient supply system for agricultural holdings today;the provision of agricultural holdings with the necessary resources is mainly carried out by private individuals;the limited ability of agricultural holdings to obtain quality resources;the lack of interest in increasing the economic literacy of the villages, they consider it sufficient if they know how to work with the land, and as a result:the number of agricultural holdings with legal status is decreasing day by day.the lack of necessary technical means, the violation of cooperative relations with other economic entities, the absence of a system for purchasing produced products.

Opportunities	Threats
<p>the increasing interest of the rural population as a result of the increase in the indicators of agricultural economic efficiency;</p> <p>the number of employed people in the village is increasing at the expense of agriculture;</p> <p>increasing possibility of attracting local investments;</p> <p>consistently high quality index of farms specializing in animal husbandry;</p> <p>that the state continuously adopts measures and programs supporting agriculture.</p>	<p>the number of people engaged in business in the agricultural sector is increasing;</p> <p>the constant juxtaposition of agricultural holdings with personal plots and household farms, which leads to the conclusion that all three types of holdings can be managed as one;</p> <p>the negative, partial satisfaction of rural interests at the expense of „speculators“;</p> <p>the sharp decrease in the number of agricultural holdings in desert zones.</p>

SWOT analysis helps to understand the factors that need to be considered when organizing an agro-industrial complex, the importance of the sector in satisfying the interests of households, society and the state.

The results of the SWOT analysis provide operating entities with information about the current situation, since the analysis also lists the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the agro-industrial complex.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Studying the digitalization and management of the agro-industrial complex as an object of research, we were convinced that its development is associated with eliminating the following problems.

- the presence of imbalances in land irrigation;
- the lack of practical and theoretical experience in the proper use of land;
- low purchase prices for some products;
- the leading position of monopoly enterprises processing agricultural products is still preserved;
- the market for providing services to agricultural workers is not sufficiently formed;
- the production of agricultural products is not fully financed;
- the presence of some outdated approaches to contracting;
- the lack of fuel and lubricants in the performance of technical services;
- the lack of service in alternative machine-tractor fleets or high costs.

We believe that the following solutions exist to eliminate the above problems:

- the organization of information advisory groups to assist agro-industrial sector employees in their work;
- increasing online accountability for all types of contracts;
- contract reviews, monitoring of production with accuracy of plan implementation;
- achieving free use of their own funds by enterprises;
- improving the service of alternative water supply associations in the use of water resources and establishing the economical use of water resources through smart meters;
- improving credit mechanisms for land improvement;
- improving the provision of service to enterprises and improving contracts concluded with service companies.

The following tasks of reforms in the agrarian sector will be solved by digitalization of agriculture;

- private ownership and a stratum of owners will be formed in the village and digital agribusiness will develop;
- economic relations in the agricultural sector are carried out in accordance with the methods and mechanisms of the digital economy;
- entrepreneurs in the agro-industry network will have material interest as a result of direct production, and effective use of this orca property will be achieved;
- real competition arises, as a result of which the interest and desire to improve production efficiency, product quality and the final economic and financial indicators of the farm increases;
- Due to the expansion of economic activities, distribution of income and freedom of entrepreneurship, activities are carried out on the basis of direct contracts with other business entities, and in order to further increase income, there is an interest in expanding production, that is, not only growing agricultural products, but also processing them and starting the production of finished products. The creation of a system for increasing land use efficiency in agriculture, reducing the cost of products and increasing export potential through the introduction of digital technologies is one of the priority areas directly related to the development of agricultural production.

As part of the measures taken to create a favorable environment for the national market of digital technologies and develop promising „digital“ startups, it is necessary to develop the production of local technological and software digital tools used in the production of agricultural products, taking into account local capabilities, geographical, ecological, geological, and biological characteristics of the region.

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